

THE ROLE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN IN RELATIONSHIP WITH CENTRAL ASIAN COUNTRIES (ANALYSIS OF 1991-1995, PUBLISHED IN THE NEWSPAPER "PEOPLE'S WORD")

Subhonova Niso Ahmadovna

Bukhara State University

Historiography, source studies and historical
research methods (by country) master

Phone: +998 (99) 703-81-26

subxonova.niso@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6692954>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022

Accepted: 02nd June 2022

Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

Central Asian states,
community, declaration,
delegation, conference,
forum, council, treaty,
Almaty meeting, assembly.

ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the general meetings, socio-political, cultural, educational and economic relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the countries of Central Asia from 1991 to 1995 on the basis of articles published in the newspaper "People's Word". It is explained in the columns of this newspaper that the political, socio-economic, spiritual and cultural processes taking place in our country and in Central Asia are objectively covered.

The article states that respect for independence, raising the political awareness of citizens, loyalty to the whole nation, traditions, freedom and liberty as the greatest blessings are the priorities of the newspaper "People's Word". The position of the Republic of Uzbekistan among the Central Asian states during this period will also be provided.

Introduction: After gaining independence, Uzbekistan has sought to establish comprehensive relations with neighboring countries in the social, economic, political and spiritual spheres. At the same time, our state has laid the foundation for the acceleration of these relations and the development of political processes. As Central Asian states gained independence, they each had to choose their own economic and political life. There is no state whose, economic and political development does not depend on its relations with its neighbors. In order for a sovereign state to recover in all respects, it

first seeks to establish warm relations with its neighbor.

Therefore, the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the independent states, while the neighboring countries are the CIS countries (Azerbaijan, Armenia, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine). It is important that these relations, especially Uzbekistan's relations with the neighboring Central Asian republics, are well covered in the newspapers.

Materials: The newspaper is one of the main means of mass media and propaganda in our social life. Its main task is to meet the needs of society for

information and spiritual potential. It provides the public with up-to-date information on socio-political, economic, cultural, educational and scientific life, and influences the formation of certain attitudes and perceptions of everyday life, historical events, the formation of political, economic, moral ideas and beliefs. It acts as an impartial mediator between government and society.

The relations between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the independent states have been described by one of the newspapers, which has been covering the political life of the country since independence.

Methods: The main task of the newspaper "People's Word" is to objectively cover the activities of the Supreme Assembly of the Republic of Uzbekistan, its bodies, the Cabinet of Ministers and local representative and executive authorities, the ongoing political, socio-economic, spiritual and moral processes. Respect for independence, raising the political awareness of citizens, educating them in the spirit of devotion to the heroic traditions of our ancestors, the recognition of freedom and liberty as the greatest blessing is an important direction of the newspaper.

Results: An article in the "People's Word" newspaper, February 18, 1992, No. 36, entitled "Declaration on Compliance with the Rules of Cooperation within the CIS" is proof of this. In this article, the member states of the Commonwealth undertake to fulfill their obligations under the Treaty establishing the Commonwealth of Independent States and other documents of the Commonwealth, in order to prevent the growth of opposition and conflict between peoples and states. Azerbaijan,

Armenia, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Representatives of Turkmenistan and Ukraine signed the declaration. At the same time, the above-mentioned declaration of 14 February 1992 in Minsk was drawn up in one original in Russian. The original is currently in the archives of the Government of the Republic of Belarus. In addition, on May 13 this year, in an article entitled "Implementation of projects of mutual interest" the Islamic Republic of Iran, the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Kyrgyz Republic, the Islamic Republic of Pakistan, the Republic of Turkey, Turkmenistan and the Republic of Uzbekistan based on the rules of friendship and solidarity, relying on the historical and cultural closeness of their peoples, the agreement was signed with a desire to develop comprehensive economic ties on the basis of equality and mutual interest.

It turns out that the first members of the CIS at the time of its formation were 11 countries. In particular, the Republic of Uzbekistan was among these

11 countries. It should be noted that the Republic of Uzbekistan also has a special place in these articles. Another proof of this is the next meeting of the CIS states in Tashkent. Under the headline "Delegations arrive in Tashkent" - "Official delegations of the independent CIS republics arrived in the Uzbek capital on May 14 to attend the Tashkent Summit".

This article addresses issues on the agenda of the Commonwealth, such as the establishment of economic ties, the restoration of broken ties, and the cessation of experiments with the military. It is noteworthy that the place to address these issues is Tashkent, according to Kazakh President Nazarbayev N. We have

long known that Tashkent is known as the city of peace. It is no coincidence that the venue for the CIS talks is Tashkent. Another such meeting took place on May 15, 1992 in Tashkent, according to the newspaper's May 16, 1992 issue. As the CIS countries took their first steps towards independence, it became clear that each was looking for a way out. In particular, opening the meeting, the first President of our country I. Karimov told each member of the Commonwealth that "each of us is going through a difficult period," and developed common approaches to economic, financial and other spheres of the Commonwealth. At the same time, the Armed Forces said that the security of the Commonwealth was the most important issue. Such approaches to independence, of course, were proposed by the first head of state of Uzbekistan I. Karimov.

Discussion: In the January 27, 1994 issue of the newspaper "People's Word" under the headline "Uzbekistan is the only country in the CIS that has managed to stop the decline in production", the views of the CIS countries on economic growth received. In it, the first President of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov said: Uzbekistan has great economic potential. But that doesn't mean we should be complacent. We, the CIS countries, need to intensify our activities and move to a qualitatively new system of management. Now, a people who have changed their minds will not be able to accept the principles of equality that were inherent in the previous system." At the same time, the first head of state announced at a meeting of the Council of the International Congress of Industrialists and Businessmen that Uzbekistan would sign an agreement with Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan on the establishment of a

single economic space, which is open to other countries passes away. The congress was scheduled to establish the Interstate Central Asian Cooperation and Development Bank, which will promote economic integration of the three Central Asian republics. Six months later, the outcome of the agreement was announced in an article in the "People's Word" newspaper, July 13, 1994, No. 136. In this issue, the heads of state and government of Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan met in Almaty on July 8.

The establishment of the Interstate Council with the participation of the Presidents and Prime Ministers of the three countries, the establishment of a permanent executive committee as its working body, and the establishment of the Central Asian Bank for Cooperation and Development are among the outstanding results of this historic meeting. The three independent states, which are just three years old, have blamed the failure to set up a transition mechanism for the bank's failure to set up a new economic relationship with the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS). That is why the young independent states of the CIS did not give the expected results.

The value of the Almaty meeting is that on the initiative of the first President of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov, a thorough mechanism for implementing the agreements has been created. The Central Asian Development Bank (ADB), which has been agreed to be established, will have a statutory fund of \$ 9 million, according to the July 12, 1994, issue 136 of the People's Word newspaper.

The Central Asian states are united not only in economic, political and social

issues, but also in the spiritual and educational spheres.

Conclusion: We know that our ancestors have always been one family, blood relatives and brothers. The destinies share the customs, traditions and rich cultures of our peoples. In this regard, in the November 226, issue 226 of the newspaper "People's Word" the first head of state I. Karimov said: It is a bold step towards further development and spreading around the world," he said. The congress of representatives of fraternal peoples living in Central Asia opened on November 21, at the magnificent Turkistan Palace (now the Friendship of Peoples) Palace in Tashkent. The congress was opened by the chairman of the organizing committee, a well-known Kyrgyz writer Chingiz Aitmatov. In particular, Chingiz Aitmatov said: "We come to Tashkent to discuss our concerns and problems, dreams and aspirations, best intentions and plans, as well as to analyze the current state of modern culture in Central Asia and to reach consensus. We have gathered," he said. The only way to further strengthen cultural and educational ties is to work together, in harmony and in harmony. The Tashkent Congress, which

has paved the way for the unification of Central Asian cultural figures, is of great importance. The fact that the participants of the conference decided to establish an international movement of the scientific and literary community of the region - the Assembly of Cultural Figures of the Peoples of Central Asia. .

The designation of Tashkent as a place of discussion for issues of national importance and development of the Central Asian states testifies to the special place and position of the Republic of Uzbekistan among the Central Asian states. In conclusion, it can be said that the first head of our state, I. Karimov, believed that the basis of all work on political and economic issues with the Central Asian states is equal cooperation. Therefore, the partner countries will benefit only if they cooperate extensively in all areas of material production. Uzbekistan's cultural and educational cooperation with Central Asian countries has not only helped to develop cooperation in science, culture and literature, but also brought the fraternal republics closer together and allowed them to live in peace and harmony in accordance with the laws of brotherhood.

References:

1. Mirziyoev Sh. Milliy taraqqiyot yo'limizni qat'iyat bilan davom ettirib, yangi bosqichga ko'taramiz. – T.: O'zbekiston, 2017. – 22-b.
2. Karimov I. Turkiston umumiy uyimiz. – T.: O'zbekiston, 1995. – 15-b.
3. Amirqul Karim. Maqsad hamkorlikni yanada mustahkamlash Xalq so'zi // 1994-yil 12-iyul, 136-son (884) 1-b.
4. Botirbekov.T., Levin.L., Drache.V. Umidbaxsh muzokaralar Xalq so'zi// 1992-yil 16-may, 94-son (344) 1-b.
5. Nishonov P., Levin L. O'zbekiston MDH davlatlari ichida ishlab chiqarish hajmi pasayishini to'xtatishga erishgan yagona mamlakatdir. Xalq so'zi // 1994-yil 27-yanvar, 19-son (767) 1-b.
6. Uz.A. MDH doirasida hamkorlik qoidalariga rioya etish bo'yicha deklaratsiya. Xalq so'zi // 1992-yil 18-fevral, 36-son (287) 1-b.

7. Uz.A. O'zaro qiziqish uyg'otuvchi loyihalarni amalga oshirish (bitim va rasmiy bayonot). Xalq so'zi // 1992-yil 13-may, 91-son (342) 1-b.
8. UzA. Qardoshlarni birlashtirgan qutlug' qurultoy. Xalq so'zi // 1995-yil 22-noyabr, 226-son (1228) 1-b.